

A novel Explainable Artificial Intelligence and secure Artificial Intelligence asset sharing platform for the manufacturing industry

Dimitris Miltiadou
UBITECH
Athens, Greece
dmiltiadou@ubitech.eu

Konstantinos Perakis
UBITECH
Athens, Greece
kperakis@ubitech.eu

Michele Sesana
TXT e-tech srl
Milano, Italy
michele.sesana@txtgroup.com

Mattia Calabresi
TXT e-tech srl
Milano, Italy
mattia.calabresi@txtgroup.com

Fenareti Lampathaki
Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions
Limassol, Cyprus
fenareti@suite5.eu

Evmorfia Biliri
Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions
Athens, Greece
evmorfia@suite5.eu

Abstract— Over the past couple of years, implementations of Artificial Intelligence (AI) have significantly risen in numerous platforms, tools and applications around the world, impacting a broad range of industries such as manufacturing towards Smart Factories and Industry 4.0, in general. Nevertheless, despite industrial AI being the driving force for smart factories, there is strong reluctance in its adoption by manufacturers due to the lack of transparency of the black-box AI models and trust behind the decisions taken, as well as the awareness of where and how it should be incorporated in their processes and products. This paper introduces the Explainable AI platform of XMANAI which takes advantage of the latest AI advancements and technological breakthroughs in Explainable AI (XAI) in order to build "glass box" AI models that are explainable to a "human-in-the-loop" without the decrease of AI performance. The core of the platform consists of a catalogue of hybrid and graph AI models which are built, fine-tuned and validated either as baseline AI models that will be reusable to address any manufacturing problem or trained AI models that have been fine-tuned for solving concrete manufacturing problems in a trustful manner through value-based explanations that are easily and effectively interpreted by humans.

Keywords— *Data Analytics, Explainable AI, AI pipelines, Architecture, Manufacturing*

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past couple of years, implementations of Artificial Intelligence (AI) have significantly risen in numerous platforms, tools and applications around the world, impacting a broad range of industries such as manufacturing. In parallel, the already established Industry 4.0 (I4.0) era has revolutionized the traditional manufacturing industry and AI is at the forefront of this revolution [1]. In particular, I4.0 has disrupted the manufacturing industry as it transformed the way products and services are designed, manufactured and delivered affecting their complete lifecycle management from beginning-of-life to end-of-life. Moreover, the forthcoming era of Industry 5.0 aims at bringing human-machine collaboration and personalization in the foreground. It is composed of new trends driven by the advancements in IoT devices and automations, and highlights the importance of AI in the resolution of existing and future manufacturing problems across diverse innovation pathways towards the 2025 Factories of the Future. Nevertheless, while AI is

definitely a key driver of the ongoing revolution of the manufacturing industry, its outstanding achievements are questioned by the increasing complexity of the black-box AI models that lack transparency [2]. AI-empowered systems are typically offering little visibility and knowledge on how decisions are taken and predictions are made since most of algorithms utilized cannot be examined in way that humans can understand specifically how and why a decision has been made. Hence, despite industrial AI being the driving force for smart factories, there is strong reluctance in the adoption by manufacturing sites because of the lack of trust behind the decisions taken and awareness of where and how it should be incorporated in the manufacturing pipeline [1]. To this end, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) was introduced as a proposed solution that will eliminate the black-box effect and head towards more transparent AI solutions that will increase its adoption by critical domains such as the manufacturing industry [2]. The goal of XAI is enable the understanding of the algorithm decisions as well as the data that influenced such a decision by end-users [3]. Hence, XAI focuses on providing explainable techniques which enable the comprehension of results increasing their trustworthiness by humans without sacrificing too much performance or accuracy.

The current paper aims to introduce the novel XMANAI Explainable AI platform which is powered by explainable AI models that inspire trust, augment human cognition and solve concrete manufacturing problems with value-based explanations. To this end, the platform takes advantage of the latest AI advancements and technological breakthroughs in XAI in order to build "glass box" AI models that are explainable to a "human-in-the-loop", without greatly sacrificing AI performance. Furthermore, the platform exploits methods and techniques to overcome data scientists' pains such as lifecycle management, security and trusted sharing of complex AI assets in order to properly address the critical barriers for the adoption of AI in the manufacturing industry, enabling the design and execution of AI pipelines from the stakeholders of the manufacturing industry.

II. METHODOLOGY

Over the past years, significant advancements have been achieved in the area of AI, such as the advanced methods for handling large amount of data in an effective and performant manner and the execution of data analysis in an intelligently and automated way. Despite these advancements, it is proven that numerous challenges have not been yet addressed as AI is currently at its infancy and the respective tools still at their early stage. Furthermore, as the inner workings of machine learning and deep learning are quite transparent to humans and algorithms become more and more complicated, fears of undetected bias, mistakes, and misconceptions creeping into decision making, naturally grow among manufacturers and practically any stakeholder of the manufacturing domain.

The main pillars of XAI, which dispels these concerns, include, among others, the increase of fairness of algorithms, the identification of potential bias in the training data, the availability of explanations of the decision-making process and how it is influenced [4]. XMANAI leverages the promising opportunity that arises from the latest advancements and compelling features of XAI in order to design and implement an Explainable AI platform that capitalizes on these emerging offerings in order to navigate the AI's "transparency paradox" that will render humans capable of fully understanding how decisions have been reached and what influenced them. The platform will enable the adoption of AI offerings into the manufacturing pipeline by effectively addressing the challenges imposed by the lack of trustworthiness of AI and the requirements of manufacturing industry's stakeholders for human/machine intelligence collaboration in the manufacturing decision making in a transparent and trusted manner.

The design and conceptualization process of the XMANAI platform was based on an agile methodology focused on the behaviour-driven requirements elicitation [5]. In particular, the requirements were extracted in the form of User Stories that depict the needs of the platform's main stakeholders, namely the data scientist, the data engineer and the business user. For each stakeholder type, the relevant user journeys were also defined. The user journeys covered several core aspects depending on stakeholder's role, spanning from the data collection, data ingestion, data handling and data infusion with domain expertise to the generation of analytics models, their evaluation and extraction of valuable insights from the AI results exploiting a variety of explainability techniques. During this process, the collected user stories were also mapped to the relevant user journey phases.

Following the requirements elicitation, the definition of the minimum set of features that address the requirements of the platform's stakeholders was performed. These features were later assessed by the stakeholders using different metrics such as their added value and their innovation along with their complexity and feasibility. This process has led to the formulation of the Minimum Viable Product (MVP) of the XMANAI platform.

The next steps in the process included the landscape analysis of the methods and technologies, best practices and applied techniques on the core building blocks of the platform. In particular, the landscape analysis covered the following core topics: a) industrial data ingestion, b) security and privacy, c)

trust consideration, d) industrial assets sharing, e) industrial assets provenance and IRP handling, f) explainability, g) visualization and visual exploration and h) collaboration. The results of the performed analysis were fed into the platform's architecture design process that is presented in Section III.

III. THE XMANAI PLATFORM

With a view to address the challenges imposed by the complex nature of the AI models, a solid methodological approach for the architecture design has been meticulously followed to ensure that the deriving reference architecture effectively builds on the requirements of manufacturing industry's stakeholders and addresses their concrete business and technical needs as extracted from the process described in Section II.

The main objective of the XMANAI platform [6] is to provide a novel Explainable AI platform which enables the manufacturing stakeholders to leverage explainable AI models in order to solve concrete manufacturing problems in a trustful manner through value-based explanations that are easily and effectively interpreted by humans. The core of the platform consists of a catalogue of hybrid and graph AI models which are built, fine-tuned and validated either as baseline AI models that will be reusable to address any manufacturing problem or trained AI models that have been fine-tuned for the different problems that are validated by four core use cases (from automotive, white goods, machinery and metrology) through a bundle of innovative manufacturing applications and services. Furthermore, the XMANAI platform effectively handles the complete lifecycle of AI assets that spans from the data uploading, data exploration, data preparation, and data sharing steps to the data analysis through the design and execution of AI pipelines accompanied by value-based explanations and proper visualizations.

To this end, an integrated Explainable AI platform is developed, composed by a set of services bundles organized into different tiers which are designed and implemented leveraging the state-of-the-art data handling, data manipulation and AI technologies and tools. The architecture of the platform follows the principles of modular services which are in turn composed of distinct components, eight services bundles in total, and are allocated into three main tiers of the architecture.

During the design process, the well-established reference architectures RAMI 4.0 [7] and IIRA [8] were thoroughly analyzed and taken into consideration. In particular, the RAMI 4.0 layers (i.e., business, functional, information, communication, integration, assets layers) and IIRA viewpoints (i.e., Business Viewpoint, Usage Viewpoint, Functional Viewpoint, Implementation Viewpoint) have been considered to ensure that all necessary design aspects have been appropriately reflected into the design specifications of the XMANAI platform. The driving principles behind the XMANAI platform's reference architecture include the clear separation of concerns and the design for flexibility and change with a focus on open-source technologies. Following an iterative process, a concrete list and positioning of the XMANAI components and their blueprints has been defined along with a set of solid workflows from the data scientist, business user and data engineer journeys that have been designed in order to define

Fig. 1: XMANAI Reference Architecture – Tiers Perspective

the interrelations between the XMANAI Platform components at high level.

From the tier perspective, the XMANAI platform is divided into three main tiers (Fig. 1): a) the **XMANAI Cloud infrastructure** which constitutes the core part of the platform and represents the centralized cloud instance of the XMANAI Platform, b) the **XMANAI On Premise Environments** which represent the parts of the XMANAI Platform that can be hosted and executed in a private cloud instance of a stakeholder and c) the **XMANAI Manufacturing Apps Portfolio** which is composed of AI manufacturing intelligence solutions that are effectively solving specific manufacturing problems. The XMANAI Cloud infrastructure is in turn composed of a) the **Core AI Management Platform** that provides all the offerings and functionalities of the platform and is responsible for the design of the data and / or AI pipelines and the orchestration of their execution; and b) the **Secure Execution Clusters (SEC)** which constitute the isolated per stakeholder organization spaces which are triggered/spawned on demand by the Core AI Management Platform, for executing data and / or AI pipelines. The XMANAI On Premise Environments facilitate the execution of the platform's functionalities on the stakeholders' environments based on the instructions that are provided by the XMANAI Cloud infrastructure in accordance with the preferences of the stakeholder.

From the services bundles perspective, the various services of the XMANAI platform are essentially developed and integrated into eight concrete bundles that are seamlessly integrated via well-defined interfaces ensuring intercommunication between them and the overall XMANAI platform (Fig. 2):

- I. **Data Collection & Governance Services bundle**, which resides on both the XMANAI Cloud infrastructure and XMANAI On-Premise Environments, undertakes the responsibility of handling how data can be consistently collected and managed, through the configuration and execution of appropriate data handling processes. To this end, the specific service bundle securely and reliably collects the data assets, either in the centralized XMANAI cloud or the on-premise (private cloud) installations, following a scheduling mechanism

suitable for APIs or a batch process that is complemented by a provenance mechanism across their lifecycle in XMANAI. To achieve this, the service bundle incorporates: a) the **Data Handler** that provides the configurable ingestion and staging functionalities with the *API Data Harvester*, the *File Data Harvester*, the *File/Data Manager* and the *Data Exporter* components, b) the **Data Anonymizer** which facilitates the anonymization of candidate data prior to making them available in XMANAI and c) the **Provenance Engine** that provides the mechanism for the lineage and changes tracking over data assets in time.

- II. **Scalable Storage Services bundle**, which resides on both the XMANAI Cloud infrastructure and XMANAI On-Premise Environments, provides the persistence modalities of the platform in order to store the available assets based on their type and the storage location (that differentiates into the centralized XMANAI cloud or on-premise depending on the installation). Finally, it provides the indexing mechanism of the metadata of all assets for query optimization and data discoverability performance.
- III. **Data Manipulation Services bundle**, which resides on both the XMANAI Cloud infrastructure and XMANAI On-Premise Environments, undertakes the data explainability and feature engineering functionalities of the platform. Its main purpose is to enable the knowledge derivation and harmonization of the available data based on the XMANAI data model as well as their manipulation towards being ML/DL-ready in order to be used in training XAI models and in executing XAI pipelines. To achieve this, the service bundle incorporates: a) the **Data Manipulation Engine** which is composed of the *Data Preparation Engine* and the *Interactive Data Exploration & Experimentation Tool* components, facilitating the data manipulation, augmentation and pre-processing for the experimentation, engineering and storage of the emerging features and b) the **Knowledge Graph Manager** which manages the XMANAI data

Fig. 2: XMANAI Reference Architecture – Services Bundles Perspective

- models and the mapping of the data into these models.
- IV. **XAI Lifecycle Management Services bundle**, which resides only in the XMANAI Cloud Infrastructure, is responsible for the management of the XAI pipelines. In detail, the specific bundle is composed of: a) the **XAI Pipeline Manager** that undertakes the step-by-step, collaborative design, validation and handling of XAI pipelines bringing together different data preparation, model engineering and explainability functionalities with the help of the *Pipeline Designer* and the *Pipeline Serving & Monitoring Engine* components, b) the **Model Engineering Engine** that provides the training, explanation generation, management, tracking and evaluation (both from performance and security perspectives) functionalities for XAI models and is composed of the *XAI Model Engineering Engine*, the *XAI Model Explanations Engine*, the *Experiment Tracking Engine* and the *XAI Model Guard*, as well as part of the *Interactive Data Exploration & Experimentation Tool* components, c) the **XAI Models Catalogue** that contains the: i) out-of-the box baseline AI models, and ii) trained artefacts per manufacturer in order to be used in the XAI pipelines.
 - V. **XAI Execution Services bundle**, which resides on both the XMANAI Cloud infrastructure and XMANAI On-Premise Environments, undertakes the execution based on the user-defined schedules of the: a) XAI models/pipelines experiments during the experimentation phase, and b) the XAI pipelines in the production phase. Hence, the specific bundle undertakes the monitoring and tracking the execution status in the Secure Execution Clusters and/or the On-Premise Environments and guarantees the storage of the model/pipeline results and associated metrics in the Scalable Storage Services with the **Execution & Orchestration Engine**.
 - VI. **XAI Insight Services bundle**, which resides on both the XMANAI Cloud infrastructure and XMANAI On-Premise Environments, constitute the main interfaces utilized by the business experts and data scientists for collaboration purposes and for gaining insights in different phases towards extracting manufacturing intelligence. These are realized through the XAI Visualization Engine with novel dashboards and diagrams visually representing the data and the XAI model results along with the necessary explanations / insights and supporting the complete experimentation process. It is composed of the *XAI Model Explanations Engine*, the *Experiment Tracking Engine*, the *XAI Model Guard* and the *Interactive Data Exploration & Experimentation Tool* components that are interacting towards the provision of the insights to the end-user.
 - VII. **Secure Asset Sharing Services bundle**, which resides only in the XMANAI Cloud Infrastructure, enables the cataloguing and trusted sharing of data and AI models across different manufacturing organizations and/or users. The specific functionalities are offered through the XAI Marketplace which is composed of the *Registry/Metadata Manager* that manages the metadata profiles of the data assets and the *Contract Manager* that handles the dynamic creation, negotiation, and finalization of non-monetary contracts for the acquisition of data assets.
 - VIII. **Platform Management Services bundle**, which resides only in the XMANAI Cloud Infrastructure, provides the access control functionalities over all the data assets based on their providers' preferences as well as the centralized user management and authentication mechanism of the platform. To this end, the specific bundle incorporates: a) the **Data Access Manager** that contains the *Policy Editor* and the *Policy Engine* components and provides the complete lifecycle manager of access policies and their enforcement to all XMANAI components, b)

the **Identity & Authorization Manager** that provides the user management lifecycle and authentication process of the platform and c) the **Mediator** which acts as the single point of information exchange between the different frontend components of the platform in order to enable the effective and efficient navigation of the user between these components.

A. The XAI Experimentation Workflow

One of the four core use cases which will validate the XMANAI platform is the FORD of Spain use case. In particular, the FORD engine plant located in Spain will leverage the offerings of the platform in order to increase the performance of its production lines as well as to minimize the planned stoppages and faults occurred during the plant's shifts. With the help of the XMANAI platform, FORD will ingest, manage and analyze data originating from Ford's corporate systems, as well as data residing on its Material Planning & Logistics systems in order to build novel XAI models which will produce valuable recommendations for optimizing the performance of the production lines in the current and successive shifts.

As explained in the previous section, the XMANAI platform has been designed to effectively handle the complete lifecycle of AI assets. One of the key novelties of the platform is built around the offerings to the business users, data scientists and data engineers for experimenting with XAI pipelines and making the transition to production.

The XAI Experimentation Workflow has been designed to support the operations performed in the platform in order to prepare the appropriate AI pipelines for the problem at hand. FORD will leverage the specific operations to achieve better plant performance. The workflow is divided into two distinct phases, namely the interactive experimentation phase and the experimentation-to-production phase.

During the interactive experimentation phase (as depicted in Fig. 3), a FORD data scientist accesses the Data Manipulation Engine through the Interactive Experimentation & Exploration Tool in order to create a new notebook environment. This results in the spawning of a new virtual machine in the available resources in the Execution & Orchestration Engine. In the next step, the FORD data scientist selects the eligible data assets that will be used (retrieved by the Scalable Storage Services after consulting the Data Access Manager) and prepares the notebook functionalities in order to develop an appropriate XAI solution for the problem at hand. The FORD data scientist executes the prepared computations at any point with the help of the Execution & Orchestration Engine. The results can be visualized or reviewed in the notebook and when he/she is satisfied with the experimentation, the transition to the experimentation-to-production phase is performed.

During the experimentation-to-production phase (as depicted in Fig. 4), a FORD data scientist can design a new XAI pipeline with the help of the XAI Pipeline Manager. At first, the FORD data scientist identifies the relevant assets that shall be leveraged (once their access policies are resolved by the Data Access Manager). At the second step, the FORD data scientist leverages the Data Manipulation Engine and the related preparation steps' configuration in order to perform interactive exploration and to gain new insights exploiting also the dataset's structure and semantics (from the Knowledge Graph Manager). In the next step, the FORD data scientist can: a) configure and view any visualization chart of interest (with the help of the XAI Visualization Engine), b) proceed to the Model Engineering Engine for working on different AI models, c) finalize the data preparation functions that will be used in the pipeline configuration.

The Model Engineering Engine can be leveraged by the FORD data scientist to create new training sessions for XAI models. In this sense, the FORD data scientist can: a) perform

Fig. 3: The XMANAI interactive experimentation phase

Fig. 4: XMANAI experimentation-to-production phase

experiments on the models to conclude on the optimal configuration (with the help of visualizations created through the XAI Visualization Engine), b) elicit explanations for the predictions of the selected model or for its operation as a whole in different ways and through different explainability techniques and c) create the relevant inference session. In the final step, the FORD data scientist stores the trained XAI model and the relevant sessions in the XAI Model Catalogue. Finally, he/she defines its access policies in the Data Access

Manager and its metadata in order to be made available in the XAI Marketplace and he/she is also given the option to annotate and explain the overall pipeline results.

IV. FINDINGS

A. Discussion

During the design phase of the XMANAI platform's reference architecture, the XMANAI consortium partners

were engaged into a series of internal roundtable discussions and brainstorming sessions, bridging the expertise within the consortium in the design and delivery of technological solutions with the expertise in the manufacturing sector services, technologies and processes in order to formulate an innovative solution. The focus of these technical sessions was to bring all the stakeholders into the same page and clarify: a) their different policies and needs when it comes to data security, infrastructure availability and b) the design and execution of AI pipelines and their needs for value-based explanations and proper visualizations of the produced results and decisions made. In this process, the scope was to identify the needs of the manufacturing sector with regards to the industrial AI and explainability. Furthermore, through these sessions, the obstacles in the adoption of the AI into the manufacturing processes due to the lack of transparency and trust in the decisions made were also identified. During this process, the main workflows of the platform referring to the collaborative AI preparation, AI experimentation, AI insights extraction and AI application workflows from the data scientist, business user and data engineer perspectives were designed, elaborated and discussed through multiple iterative sessions.

The major challenges faced during this design phase of XMANAI platform's reference architecture can be divided into two main axes: a) the integration challenges and b) the XAI challenges.

From the integration perspective, as the XMANAI platform's reference architecture is composed of three different tiers residing on different network locations (cloud vs on premise installations) with eight distinct services bundles incorporating 12 different components, the complexity of the integration process is increased. Each service bundle is leveraging different state-of-the-art technologies and tools which should be successfully and smoothly integrated into the different layers ensuring their proper intercommunication and interaction for the realization of the platform's functionalities. As these technologies and tools are in various levels of maturity and bounded to different specifications and programming languages peculiarities and limitations, the complexity of the aspired integration is affected. There are also no commonly accepted standards for XAI models or pipelines definition and interoperability, which makes the integration of different technologies harder. Furthermore, for several aspects of the AI pipelines diverse needs from the different stakeholders should be addressed. This results to the utilization and possible combination of different technologies and libraries for a specific platform functionality resulting on the increase of the complexity of the integration activities. Furthermore, AI pipelines require a level of modularity from the underlying components which are combined, however there are strong dependencies between them in order to effectively handle the ML development and deployment lifecycle which is rather challenging.

From the XAI perspective, the collaborative AI preparation, which includes all the steps to make available and comprehensive the XAI pipeline results leveraging appropriate manufacturing data for a business problem, is becoming more complex due to the need of constant iterations between data scientists and business users. In the AI experimentation phase, the preparation of the appropriate AI pipelines for the problem at hand through the gaining of

insights of the existing data, the preparation and manipulation of the data and the experimentation of the models towards the discovery of the optimal solution is also challenging. Different semantics and structure accompany different datasets even from the same data source, which requires discussions among business users themselves, but also between business users and data scientists, to provide explanations over the data. In addition, the AI insights extraction and AI application should provide the appropriate AI insights in an understandable, explicit manner in which the perspective of the business user is the most critical. To this direction, the available XAI solutions and approaches are not yet mature enough and further research is required in many areas since the nature, the structure and the format of an explanation has not been yet formalized in literature and tools [9], not to mention concrete metrics that can be utilized to assess its utility and added value depending on the targeted stakeholder. In addition to this, the challenge of the trade-off between model explainability and performance is not yet effectively solved, hence a more understandable model might not be as accurate as possible [10]. From the literature, it is also evident that there are great challenges still to be resolved in order to be able to introduce explainability in Deep Learning models [4]. In fact, there is still fertile ground for research for non-image or non-text and other heterogeneous other, such as sequences, graphs, and spatio-temporal data, which are until now not well explained when used in AI [2]. Significant research effort has been invested in the ML models development lifecycle, when it comes to the training, deployment and management of ML models, however there is a lack of support for the explainability features in this lifecycle management. Finally, scalability in existing XAI models and methods still requires more research as the desired computations can be costly for multivariable problems.

V. CONCLUSION

The scope of the current paper is to introduce the XMANAI Explainable AI platform that aims to provide the innovative environment where the manufacturing stakeholders will be able to exploit explainable AI while trying to resolve critical manufacturing problems, through value-based explanations that increase their trust in the AI models and can easily and effectively interpreted by humans. The XMANAI Explainable AI platform offers a catalogue of baseline and fine-tuned trained "glass box" AI models which can be leveraged to build innovative manufacturing applications and services that can be introduced into the manufacturing pipeline and revolutionize it. The platform also provides the secure and trusted environment where the complete lifecycle of AI assets is performed, starting from the data harvesting, data curation and exploration to their utilization in advanced data analysis in which value-based explanations are provided along with the proper visualizations. The platform exploits the latest advancements in the area of data analysis, AI and XAI in order to increase the stakeholder's trust and involvement in the AI process to address critical barriers for the adoption of AI in the manufacturing sector. The paper presented the reference architecture of the XMANAI Explainable AI platform, elaborating on the different tiers and the services bundles across these tiers and documented the technical challenges that have been introduced.

The next steps of our work include the continuous delivery of the updated versions of the XMANAI Explainable AI platform (which is currently on its alpha version) based on feedback from its validation through four core use cases of the manufacturing sector.

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